

PRIME PETE

PRIMARY EDUCATION PHYSICAL EDUCATION TEACHER EDUCATION

Open course platform

Alina Lemling, Dana Masarykova

Co-funded by the
Erasmus+ Programme
of the European Union

This work is licensed under the Creative Commons Attribution 4.0 International License. <http://creativecommons.org/licenses/by/4.0/>

Technical sheet

Title: Open course platform

Authors: Alina Lemling, Dana Masarykova

Number of pages: 17

Year: 2023

Cite as: Lemling, A., & Masarykova, D. (2023). *Open course platform*. [PRIME PETE Project - Report Intellectual Output #9]. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.10710174>

Project: Primary Education Physical Education Teacher Education

Project Coordinator: Claude Scheuer (until February 2023), Alina Lemling (from February 2023)

Funder: European Commission

Programme: Erasmus+ Key Action 2: Cooperation for innovation and the exchange of good practices 2020

Action Type: Strategic Partnerships for Higher Education

Reference: 2020-1-LU01-KA203-063257

Timeline: December 2020 – August 2023

Project Sheet: <https://ec.europa.eu/programmes/erasmus-plus/projects/eplu-project-details/#project/2020-1-LU01-KA203-063257>

For further information on the PRIME PETE Project please follow the link:

Website: www.primepete.com

Project partners:

The authors wish to acknowledge the contribution of the Primary Education Physical Education Teacher Education (PRIME PETE) project team for the development of the outputs here referenced for PRIME PETE (2023).

No.	Institution	Involved researchers
1	University of Luxembourg, Luxembourg	Claude Scheuer (until February 23), Alina Lemling (from Feb 23), Manolis Adamakis (from June 21), Richard Bailey (May-December 21), Sandra Heck (until June 22)
2	Libera Università di Bolzano, Italy	Attilio Carraro, Partizia Tortella (until March 21), Giampaolo Santi (from December 21)
3	Universidad de Sevilla	Francis Ries, Matilde Mora Fernández (until March 22)
4	Faculdade de Motricidade Humana (FMH), Universidade de Lisboa, Portugal	Marcos Onofre, Nuno Ferro, António Rodrigues, João Martins
5	Dublin City University, Ireland	Susan Marron, Frances Murphy
6	Trnavská Univerzita v Trnave, Slovakia	Dana Masarykova, Jana Labudova
7	European Physical Education Association [EUPEA], Luxembourg	Tamas Csanyi, Yiannis Gryparis (until September 21), Martin Holzweg, Rose-Marie Repond

Disclaimer: The European Commission support for the production of this publication does not constitute an endorsement of the contents, which reflect the views only of the authors, and the Commission cannot be held responsible for any use, which may be made of the information contained therein.

Table of contents

Technical sheet	2
Table of contents	4
1. Introduction	5
2. Development of the open course platform	6
3. Structure of the PRIME PETE open course platform.....	6
3.1 About us	9
3.2 Partners.....	9
3.3 Intellectual Outputs	10
3.4 Teaching Modules	12
3.4.1 Overarching Elements.....	14
3.4.2 Teaching Modules.....	14
3.4.3 Teaching Mirco-Modules	15
3.5 The Self-Check tool	16
3.6 Glossary.....	16
3.7 Contact us	16
4. Conclusion.....	16
References	17

1. Introduction

To present the steps and thus the results of the project to the public, an open course platform in the English language was created in the form of a project website. An easy-accessible and user-friendly open course platform making available the project outcomes was developed in cooperation with the external provider Allegra, s. r. o., Slovakia in form of a website. All developed outputs, especially the course modules and micro-modules are downloadable. The most appropriate way to do so was an open course platform, from where the course modules can be easily downloaded by their future users.

The users that may be interested in the open course platform are:

- Teacher education institutions;
- Teacher educators;
- Researchers active in the field of teacher education;
- NGO's (e.g., research associations, teacher associations, etc.);
- Stakeholders and policy makers in charge of teacher education.

According to our knowledge, the presented [online course platform](#) designed within the PETE PE project is the first one that provides access to comprehensive primary PETE programme that is based on a conceptual framework and a target teacher profile. The platform was constructed to provide easy access and manageable interface for its users. The open course platform allows future users to access the primary PETE programme and the various course modules, as well as to find any relevant supporting information and resources. The course modules and resources are ready for implementation by the potential users. As already mentioned, the open course platform was designed as an outcome of PRIME PETE Erasmus+ project. Its design was led by University of Luxembourg with an external provider and the support of all partners and a special contribution of Trnava University. All partners contributed to development of the platform and its content. All contents provided at the platform were developed by researchers and teacher educators from respective Universities comprising the project team.

2. Development of the open course platform

The open course platform was developed to make available project outcomes and ensure sustainability of the project results after project lifetime. The platform is developed in cooperation with an external provider, taking under consideration the following aspects:

- All project results and developed IO's to be published on the platform and available with open access, with special focus on the modular PETE programme consisting of course modules and micro modules for primary PETE;
- The platform to be easy-accessible and user-friendly;
- The platform to facilitate an easy and flexible implementation of the modular PETE programme in different contexts;
- Regular updates of the platform by external provider, based on project partners requirements.
- protection of the materials published using CREATIVE COMMONS LICENSE.

The construction of the platform included the following steps:

- Formulation of a brief with specifications to inform potential external providers about the needs of the project partners regarding the platform;
- Call for bids by external providers;
- Selection of the most adequate offer;
- Cooperation with the external provider selection to finalize the platform;
- Finalization of all IO's in a platform appropriate format;
- Launch of the platform (16th May 2023);
- Feedback from participants on the platform.

3. Structure of the PRIME PETE open course platform

The open course platform was created in the form of a project website to present project results and make them visible and accessible for the project target groups. The platform can be reached via the website's link (<https://www.primepete.com>). The start page leads the user to a . The tabs in the upper part of the start page also remain when clicking through the subpages and reflect the structure of the platform (Figure 2).

Figure 2. Upper part of the landing page

The platform thus contains the following tabs:

- About Us;
- Partners;
- Intellectual Outputs;
- Teaching Modules;
- Self-Check;
- Glossary and; and
- Contact Us.

The content of the individual sub-pages is explained in the following sections. In addition, there is a slider in the centre of the landing page showing potential PE related pictures. These images

Open course platform

are underpinned by headlines that are intended to arouse the reader's interest and at the same time provide the opportunity to obtain further information on the topic via an embedded link. Three central elements were selected from the steps of the project, which are accessible here via the slider on the start page.

“LEARNING TO TEACH - Devoted to Primary Physical Education” leads the reader to an overview of the projects’ different IOs.

“BEING A PE TEACHER - Primary Physical Education Teacher Profile” leads the reader to the result of IO#3 or identification of how PE teacher profile should be.

“MODULAR TEACHER EDUCATION PROGRAMME - Inspiring Physical Education Teacher Education” leads the reader to the result of IO#5 – designed modules and micro-modules for PRIME PETE.

Below the slider, a short description of the project is provided, and the ten steps of the project are shown graphically. In the lower part of the landing page there is also the option to access the sub-pages Project Partners, Project Mission & Objectives and the Contact us function (Figure 3).

Figure 3. Lower part of the landing page

3.1 About us

The *About us* page provides the reader with an insight into the PRIME PETE mission, the motivation and the goals of the project.

3.2 Partners

The *Partners* page shows the information about the partners involved in the project. Each partner institution is presented with a picture and general information. More information for each

Open course platform

partner institution can be called up using the “Show more” function and the “Visit site” button that provide a link to visit the respective partner's website (Figure 4).

Figure 4. Partners Subpage

3.3 Intellectual Outputs

The *Intellectual Outputs* page gives an overview of the reports from each output (Figure 5). These objectives were achieved by developing step-by-step the intellectual outputs of the project which could be described by the following scheme:

Figure 1. Steps of the PRIME PETE project

Open course platform

The overview is arranged in the order in which they were developed in the project. Intellectual outputs #1-#4 build the basis for the development of the modular primary PE programme, which is the core of the Primary Education Physical Education Teacher Education (PRIME PETE) project resulted in the open course platform. Readers can look at each intellectual output by clicking on the *Read more* button.

Figure 5. Intellectual Outputs Subpage

Open course platform

In the case of very extensive outputs, the content was usually created in such a way that readers can unpack it if necessary, using accordion or button functions, so that it does not appear overloaded at first glance and more information can be requested if necessary (Figure 6).

Figure 6. Accordion function in IO#2

3.4 Teaching Modules

The tab *Teaching Modules* leads to the created PRIME PETE modules, micro-modules and overarching elements. The Teaching modules overview page shows the three different types of

teaching elements - Overarching Elements, Teaching Modules and Teaching Micro-Modules. (Figure 7).

Overarching Elements
Read more

Teaching Modules
Read more

Teaching Micro Modules
Read more

Modules and Micro Modules Overview

Search:

Module (M) and Micro Module (MM) and Overarching Elements (OE)	Partner	Element	Setting	D1	D1K1	D1K2	D1K3	D1K4	D1K5	D1K6	D1K7	D1S1	D1S2	D1S3	D
Planning and Implementation of physical education	Uni Luc	M	TP & NP	no	no	no	no	no	no	no	no	no	no	no	no
Planning and Implementation of Physical Education: Child appropriate Physical Education	Uni Luc	MM	TP & NP	no	no	no	no	no	no	no	no	no	no	no	no

Figure 7. Teaching Modules Subpage

The modular primary PETE programme consists of course modules and micro-modules based on the theoretical and methodological framework for primary PETE (IO#4). It was developed in form

Open course platform

of pdf documents available for download. The modules and micro modules are developed in English language. In addition, the programme also contains three overarching elements that are less specific to physical education but can enrich the education of prospective primary school physical education teachers.

In addition, this page contains a comprehensive table (Modules and Micro-Modules overview), showing the dimensions and sub-dimension intended to be reached from the PRIME PETE Teacher profile.

By clicking on the respective *Read more* button of the Course Overarching Elements, Teaching Modules and Teaching Micro-Modules one can access more detailed information.

3.4.1 Overarching Elements

This subpage contains the three Overarching Elements

- Teacher as a Reflective Practitioner in PE;
- Research in PE;
- Professional Placement in PE.

Clicking on the respective Flipping Box takes you to the corresponding sub-page and provides information on how the Overarching Element is structured.

3.4.2 Teaching Modules

The Teaching Modules subpage contains an overview of all thirteen modules included in the programme. These are also displayed in flipping boxes and can be clicked on to get more information. The individual modules contain an overview of the content of the module, the proposed ECTS points, the total workload, teaching methodologies, facilities, indicative content and the addressed dimensions from the Teacher Profile. Furthermore, the learning objectives of the module are described. If interested, the module description can be downloaded via the Download PDF button. The download document also contains an exemplary resource on how the module can be embedded in the semester schedule as well as guiding material.

Teaching Physical Education

The module Teaching Physical Education is a subject/module of the Master of Teaching in PE oriented to prepare preservice specialist teachers to intervening in the PE teaching at the 1st and 2nd schooling level (5-9y & 10-11y), together equivalent to primary schooling level in most European countries. In Portugal, specialist PE teachers use to act in primary school as substitutes of generalist teachers (not officially, namely in the private system) or as support teachers or extra-curricular physical activities (officially, mainly in the public system).

The module is organize to prepare preservice teachers to developed their interpretative, prescriptive and justificatory knowledge about the childhood motor development (and its interactions with the social, emotional and cognitive ones), the national curricular aims and contents, the quality of PE lessons planning, classroom management, and assessment, and the integration of PE in primary schools as a compulsory subject, both in its specific or multidisciplinary contribution

Suggested Number of ECTS

3

TEACHING METHODOLOGIES

Lecture – expositive and reflexive teaching

Group Work (workshop) – small group of 25 students – Problem solving / debates / discussion

Real practical lessons with primary pupils in the gym / observational / discussion

Dimensions Core

D1K1, D1K2, D1K3
D2S1, D2S2, D2S3

Indicative Content

- Integration of PE in the Curriculum Development Plan for the 1st cycle.
- Analysis, in real situations, of the PE Teaching-Learning Process in the 1st cycle.
- Organization and management of teaching

MODULE LEARNING OUTCOMES

- LO1: Identify the biological and social characteristics of motor development in childhood;
- LO2: Identify the purposes of the Physical Education (PE) educational project within the scope of the global educational project of the 1st cycle of basic education and PE;
- LO3: Critically analyses the relationship between PE and Physical and Sports Activities;
- LO4: Identify the characteristics of teaching quality and learning in the 1st of school
- LO5: Plan and evaluate the learning contents of the PE program in the 1st cycle, ensuring the differentiation of teaching according to the educational needs of children
- LO6: Justify the integration of the PE curriculum area in the 1st cycle multidisciplinary educational project.

[Download PDF](#)

Figure 8. Module Example

3.4.3 Teaching Mirco-Modules

The subpage *Teaching Micro-Modules* contains an overview of all 14 micro-modules included in the programme. These are also displayed in flipping boxes, grouped if they belong to a common superordinate module and can be clicked on if necessary to obtain more information. The micro-

Open course platform

modules are structured in the same way as the modules, except that they contain two buttons, one for downloading the PDF version but also another Download the Support Material button, which provides directly related teaching materials.

3.5 The Self-Check tool

The *Self-Check tool tab* leads to a subpage containing a tool that can be used to check the education programme at the readers own institution. One of the important outcomes of the project was the formulation of the dimensions and sub-dimensions, which helped to develop the modules and micro-modules. These dimensions and sub-dimensions of the PRIME PETE Teacher Profile could serve as a basis for a self-check process in higher education institutions (HEIs) to evaluate the quality of the PETE programmes provided by the HEIs and also could be a motivation for extending the current PETE programmes.

With this checklist, educators who want to embed the PRIME PETE programme or parts of it at their institution, have the possibility to check their own, prevailing programme for the coverage of the respective dimensions. In the event that one's current programme does not cover all dimensions of the PE Teacher Profile, suitable modules or micro-modules can be selected to complement one's programme.

3.6 Glossary

Since the outputs of the project uses numerous terms that may have different interpretations a PRIME PETE glossary is included here.

3.7 Contact us

The *Contact us* tab contains contact details about the project coordinator at the University of Luxembourg as well as a contact form that offers the possibility to get in touch with the project partners.

4. Conclusion

The PRIME PETE platform brings together the results of the 2,5-year Erasmus+ project. The platform offers the public the opportunity to view the results.

Open course platform

The platform was launched in May 2023 its maintenance is guaranteed for the following 10 years (2023-2033). The open course platform (<https://www.primepete.com>) includes reports for all the 10 IOs, as well as a description of each module and micro-module proposed by the project partners, together with slides and further materials relating to each micro-module (see Marron et al., 2023). Additionally, a handbook with guidance material and recommendations (see Masarykova et al., 2023) is available on the platform in pdf format. Further tools and information regarding evaluation methods, derived from the IOs #6 (see Adamakis et al. 2023) and #7 (see Adamakis & Scheuer, 2023) are also provided on the web platform.

The project platform provides a good basis to keep the project active and accessible beyond the project duration. For example, the platform will be disseminated through different networks such as partner organisation networks, European Physical Education Association (EUPEA) network, social media). To ensure the longevity of the project, an exploitation and sustainability plan was generated in IO #10 that aims at exactly this goal and contains strategies to meet it, see [Exploitation and Sustainability Plan on the website](#).

References

- Adamakis, M., & Scheuer, C. (2023). *Evaluation study and report* [PRIME PETE Project - Report Intellectual Output #7].
- Adamakis, M., Scheuer, C., Carraro, A., & Santi, G. (2023). *Method and tool to evaluate the PETE course modules and micro-modules* [PRIME PETE Project - Report Intellectual Output #6].
- Masarykova, D., Lemling, A., Marron, S., & Murphy, F. (2023). *Handbook and guidance material for the implementation of the primary PETE programme* [PRIME PETE Project - Report Intellectual Output #8].